

THE 1937-1938 PURGES OF THE UZBEK NATIONAL INTELLECTUALS: CULTURAL CONSEQUENCES OF STALINIST REPRESSION

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Annotation. *This article examines the 1937–1938 purges of Uzbek national intellectuals within the broader framework of Stalinist repression and its cultural consequences. Drawing on sources in Uzbek, Russian, Turkish, and English, the study situates the repression of leading writers, educators, and scholars within Stalin’s nationality policy and the logic of the Great Terror. It highlights how prominent figures such as Abdulla Qodiriy, Abdulhamid Cho‘lpon, and Abdurauf Fitrat were executed alongside thousands of others, effectively silencing a generation of intellectual leadership. The analysis underscores the devastating cultural losses that followed: the rupture of literary traditions, the decline of education and scholarship, the imposition of strict ideological controls on art and language, and the erasure of pre-Soviet heritage. Furthermore, the article explores how the memory of these events was suppressed under Soviet rule, and later reinterpreted and commemorated in post-Soviet Uzbekistan as part of a national project of historical justice. The study argues that the destruction of Uzbekistan’s intellectual elite in 1937–1938 represented not only a political purge but also a deliberate cultural catastrophe with long-lasting effects on national identity.*

Keywords: *Great Purge (1937–1938), Uzbek intellectuals, Stalinist repression, Cultural consequences, Jadid movement.*

ЧИСТКИ УЗБЕКСКОЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОЙ ЭЛИТЫ В 1937–1938 ГОДАХ: КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ СТАЛИНИСТСКИХ РЕПРЕССИЙ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются репрессии 1937–1938 годов в отношении узбекских интеллектуалов в более широком контексте сталинских репрессий и их культурных последствий. Опираясь на источники на узбекском, русском, турецком и английском языках, исследование рассматривает репрессии в отношении ведущих писателей, педагогов и ученых в рамках национальной политики Сталина и логики Большого террора. В ней подчеркивается, как такие выдающиеся деятели, как Абдулла Кодирий, Абдулхамид Чолпон и Абдурауф Фитрат, были казнены вместе с тысячами других, что фактически привело к утрате целого поколения интеллектуального лидерства. Анализ подчеркивает последовавшие за этим разрушительные культурные потери: разрыв литературных традиций, упадок образования и науки, введение строгого идеологического контроля над искусством и языком, а также уничтожение досоветского наследия. Кроме того, в статье исследуется, как память об этих событиях была подавлена при советской власти, а затем переосмыслена и увековечена в постсоветском Узбекистане в рамках национального проекта исторической справедливости. В исследовании утверждается, что уничтожение интеллектуальной элиты Узбекистана в 1937–1938 годах представляло собой не только политическую чистку, но и преднамеренную культурную катастрофу, оказавшую долгосрочное влияние на национальную идентичность.

Ключевые слова: Большой террор (1937–1938), узбекские интеллектуалы, сталинские репрессии, культурные последствия, движение джадидов.

INTRODUCTION

The Stalinist purges of the late 1930s constitute one of the most destructive episodes in the history of the Soviet Union. While the terror engulfed the entire country, its impact on the non-Russian republics was particularly profound, where the elimination of local elites not only consolidated Moscow’s political control but also dismantled cultural autonomy. In Uzbekistan, the Great Purge of 1937–1938 marked the annihilation of a vibrant generation of intellectuals, writers, and

educators who had pioneered the modernization of Uzbek literature, education, and national consciousness in the 1920s.

The purges did not emerge in a vacuum. They were preceded by collectivization, forced sedentarization, and early repressions against alleged nationalist organizations. By the mid-1930s, Stalinist policy increasingly equated national identity with political subversion, rendering Uzbek intellectual life a prime target. The arrests and executions of key figures such as Abdulla Qodiriy, Abdulhamid Cho‘lpon, and Abdurauf Fitrat represented more than personal tragedies; they symbolized the destruction of a cultural renaissance and the enforced severance of links with Uzbekistan’s historical heritage.

This article seeks to analyze the purges of 1937–1938 in Uzbekistan through four interconnected lenses. First, it explores the historical background of Soviet nationalities policy and the ideological context that paved the way for repression. Second, it details the processes of mass arrest, trial, and execution that decimated Uzbekistan’s political and intellectual elite. Third, it examines the cultural consequences, highlighting the silencing of literary voices, the erosion of educational and artistic institutions, and the imposition of ideological conformity. Finally, it investigates how the memory of the purges has been repressed, rediscovered, and commemorated from the Soviet period to contemporary Uzbekistan. By situating the tragedy of 1937–1938 within both its historical and cultural dimensions, the study demonstrates how Stalinist repression shaped not only politics but also the long-term trajectory of Uzbek cultural identity.

Historical Background

In the 1920s, Soviet nationality policy initially promoted *korenizatsiya* (indigenization), encouraging local languages and elites. However, by the late 1920s–early 1930s, Stalin’s regime shifted toward centralization and suspicion of “bourgeois nationalism.” In Uzbekistan, the Jadid modernizers and early national communists who had fostered Uzbek language, literature, and cultural autonomy became targets. A 1929 Uzbek party congress launched a crackdown under the

pretext of fighting “factionalism.” The first victims were those leaders and intellectuals striving to revive national culture and improve living conditions; prominent Uzbek Bolsheviks like T. Рыскулов, A. Рахимбаев, N. Туракулов and others were accused of nationalism.¹ In late 1929, the secret nationalist group *Milliy Istiqlol* (“National Independence”) led by Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov was uncovered: 38 people were arrested, this number later increased to 87. The case was moved to Moscow and eventually all were *qatag'on qilil* (genocide, mass extermination). This early repression of national elites set the stage for the Great Purge to come.²

Stalin’s ideological turn in the 1930s intensified repression nationwide. His maxim that class struggle sharpened under socialism rationalized sweeping terror.³ Collectivization and forced sedentarization hit Central Asia hard: by 1930, Uzbekistan, like other republics, was purging “kulaks” (wealthy farmers) and NEP-era traders. Thousands of Uzbek households were labeled kulaks and deported, even though “kulak” was an alien category in a predominantly poor peasant society.⁴ Such coercive policies provoked local resistance — from sporadic peasant uprisings to the lingering Basmachi insurgency — which in turn reinforced the regime’s sense of vulnerability and served to justify subsequent waves of repression.⁵

By the mid-1930s, political nonconformity was routinely branded as counter-revolutionary. The assassination of Leningrad party chief Sergey Kirov in December 1934 served as a critical pretext for Stalin to unleash mass terror under the guise of eradicating ‘Kirov’s enemies.’ In the ensuing years, a wave of show

¹ Muhabbat Gaffarovna Sayidova. “S kakoy tsel’yu intelligentsiya Uzbekistana repressirovalas’ v epokhu stalinizma?” *Aktual'nye Issledovaniya*, 1 (28), 2021.

² Tarix-Sinaps. “Milliy Ittihod, ‘Milliy Istiqlol.’” *Tarix, Sinaps – Glossariy*, 2024, <https://tarix.sinaps.uz/lugat/milliy-ittihod-milliy-istiqlol/>, accessed: 15.08.2025.

³ Barry McLoughlin and Kevin McDermott, eds., *Stalin’s Terror: High Politics and Mass Repression in the Soviet Union* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2003), s. 55-59.

⁴ *Amerika Ovozi*, “O‘zbek ziyolilarining so‘nggi maskaniga aylangan Toshkent qatlg‘ohlari,” *Amerika Ovozi*, 4.11.2006.

⁵ Terry Martin, *The Affirmative Action Empire: Nations and Nationalism in the Soviet Union, 1923–1939*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2001; Sarah Cameron, *The Hungry Steppe: Famine, Violence, and the Making of Soviet Kazakhstan*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2018.

trials and purges devastated the Party elite: approximately 70 percent of the Central Committee elected in 1934 and over half of the 1,966 delegates to the 17th Party Congress were subsequently arrested, exiled, or executed.⁶ Uzbekistan was no exception – even before 1937, dozens of Uzbek officials had been purged in fabricated cases like the “Kasymov affair” and “Inagamov affair”.

Crucially, Stalin’s growing mistrust of non-Russian elites rendered national identity itself politically suspect.⁷ In the Uzbek SSR, the flourishing literary and intellectual milieu of the 1920s and 1930s came under assault: Abdulla Qodiriy, author of Uzbekistan’s first modern novels, was executed in 1938, while many other writers, educators, and scholars were branded ‘nationalists’ and silenced. Earlier figures such as Mahmud Khoja Behbudiy, a leading Jadid reformer executed in 1919, symbolized the vulnerability of Uzbek cultural leadership to Soviet repression. Thus, what had once been celebrated as national revival was redefined by Moscow as a threat to centralization.⁸ Moscow feared that Uzbekistan’s “traditional and historical cultural identity” nurtured nationalist sentiments that could undermine Soviet unity. Uzbek intellectuals who advocated for cultural autonomy or preservation of Uzbek language and traditions were branded “potential subversives”.⁹ Likewise, the strong Muslim identity of Uzbek society was deemed a rival ideology; Islamic institutions were dismantled (Sharia courts abolished, madrassas closed by 1928) and ulema (clergy) repressed. Even before 1937, Uzbek religious figures were coerced into absurd confessions (e.g. a 1935 NKVD case forced Tashkent imams to confess to spying for Japan, “the only country defending Muslims”). These trends – the assault on local elites, forced socio-economic upheaval, and ideological uniformity – form the backdrop against

⁶ Sheila Fitzpatrick, *Everyday Stalinism: Ordinary Life in Extraordinary Times: Soviet Russia in the 1930s* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1999); Oleg Khlevniuk, *Stalin: New Biography of a Dictator* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2015); Robert Service, *Stalin: A Biography* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2004), 271–75.

⁷ İsmail Polat, *Özbekistan Birinci Cumhurbaşkanı İslam Kerimov: Milli İdeolojinin Oluşumu*, (Ankara: Astana Yay., 2024), s.137-138.

⁸ Martin, *ibid.*; Khalid, Adeeb. *Making Uzbekistan: Nation, Empire, and Revolution in the Early USSR*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2015, p. 102.

⁹ Douglas Northrop. *Veiled Empire: Gender and Power in Stalinist Central Asia*. (Cornell University Press, 2004).

which the Great Purge struck Uzbekistan’s national intelligentsia with full force in 1937–1938.

Repression Process (1937–1938)

The Great Terror reached its peak in Uzbekistan in 1937–1938, as part of Stalin’s empire-wide purge. Under Nikolai Yezhov, the NKVD carried out mass operations through extrajudicial ‘troikas’ and the Military Collegium of the Supreme Court (VKVS). In Uzbekistan, repression began at the top: the leadership of the Uzbek Communist Party was decimated. In the months of August–September 1937 alone, several thousand individuals were confined to the inner prisons of the republican NKVD, including nearly the entire Uzbek party elite.¹⁰ The OGPU/NKVD fabricated charges of ‘sabotage’ and nationalist conspiracy against high-ranking Uzbek officials, most notably Fayzulla Khodjaev, former head of government, and Akmal Ikramov, First Secretary of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan. Along with their colleagues, they were accused of forming an ‘anti-Soviet nationalist bloc’ and engaging in acts of diversion against the Soviets. In 1938, Khodjaev, Ikramov, and others were transferred to Moscow to stand trial in the infamous ‘Trial of the Twenty-One,’ after which they were executed. Their downfall epitomized the obliteration of Uzbekistan’s national elite during the Great Terror.¹¹ By mid-1938, over 60% of all district, city, and provincial party secretaries in Uzbekistan had been arrested, and a further 114 local secretaries were purged in late 1938. The purge thus wiped out the republic’s political leadership, replacing them with Moscow-loyal cadres.

Even more infamous was the campaign against Uzbekistan’s cultural and intellectual elite. Historians note that ‘nearly the entire flower of the Uzbek intelligentsia’—writers, poets, scholars, educators, and artists—fell victim to the terror. Figures such as Abdulla Qodiriy, Cho‘lpon, and Abdurauf Fitrat were executed in 1938, while countless others were imprisoned or silenced. This

¹⁰ Martin, *ibid.*; Getty, J. Arch & Oleg Naumov. *The Road to Terror: Stalin and the Self-Destruction of the Bolsheviks, 1932–1939*. (Yale University Press, 1999).

¹¹ Robert Conquest, *The Great Terror: A Reassessment*. Oxford University Press, 1990.; Getty & Naumov, *ibid.*

decapitation of cultural leadership not only obliterated the republic’s vibrant literary and scholarly scene but also redefined national identity itself as politically suspect.¹² Mass arrests on fabricated charges were carried out in successive waves. As contemporaries recalled, ‘today the communications workers are rounded up; tomorrow the teachers; the next day the artists; then the writers.’ No stratum of society was left untouched: the terror proceeded methodically, group by group, until the fabric of Uzbek cultural and professional life was torn apart.¹³ Those arrested were typically accused of “bourgeois nationalism,” pan-Turkism, espionage or belonging to imaginary anti-Soviet organizations. One by one, Uzbekistan’s cultural luminaries were taken by the NKVD. Notably, the great Uzbek writers Abdulla Qodiriy, Abdulhamid Cho’lpon, and Abdurauf Fitrat – regarded as the founding fathers of modern Uzbek literature – were all arrested in 1937 (Fitrat in April, Cho’lpon in July, Qodiriy at year’s end).¹⁴ Detainees were tortured into signing confessions, though Abdulla Qodiriy famously scrawled on his indictment sheet that he did not accept the false accusations. Many intellectuals were implicated in the so-called ‘Milliy Ittihad’ (National Union) case—an alleged underground nationalist network—or were accused of collusion with Trotskyites and foreign spies. Such charges, fabricated to fit the template of empire-wide purges, provided the pretext for eliminating Uzbekistan’s cultural and political elite.¹⁵

The climax of the Great Terror in Uzbekistan came on 4 October 1938, remembered as ‘the bloodiest day in Uzbek history.’ On that day, the Military Collegium of the USSR Supreme Court in Moscow sentenced 507 Uzbek political prisoners to death. Among those condemned were the literary giants Abdulla Qodiriy, Cho’lpon, and Abdurauf Fitrat—revered as the classics of modern Uzbek

¹² Kamoludin Abdullaev, “Repressions in Central Asia in the 1930s: Nationalism, Pan-Turkism and Islam in the Soviet Discourse,” *Central Asian Survey* 19, no. 3–4 (2000): 317–331.

¹³ Getty & Naumov, *ibid.*

¹⁴ Peppertephoenix, “Cho’lpon and Abdulla Qodiriy,” *Resisting Empire* (blog), August 27 2023; *Xabar.uz*, “Qodiriy nega qatag’on qilingan?,” *Xabar.uz*, April 11 2018.

¹⁵ Abdullaev, *ibid.*

literature—as well as Khudoybergan Devonov, the republic’s pioneering filmmaker and photographer. The executions also claimed the lives of leading scholars and cultural figures, including the first Uzbek literary critics Kayum Ramazon and Otajon Khojimov, folklorist Ziyo Saidov, journalist Qozi Olim Yunusov, and historian Pulat Soliev. In a single day, the republic’s intellectual and artistic leadership was annihilated.¹⁶ They were shot at a secret execution ground in Tashkent’s outskirts (Aqtape in the Yunusabad district), where the “best part of the Uzbek intelligentsia” was annihilated. In total, about 7,000 Uzbeks were executed in 1937–1938 at the height of the purge. The victims truly represented “*the flower of our nation – genuine leaders, advanced intellectuals, the finest writers and cultural figures*”, as one account laments.¹⁷

The repression process was marked by show trials, coerced confessions, and secret executions. NKVD troikas dispensed summary ‘justice’ in camera, frequently fulfilling arrest and execution quotas set by Moscow. Stalin insisted that all accused confess before execution, a directive that encouraged interrogators to use extensive torture to secure scripted admissions of guilt. In Uzbekistan, such confessions included fantastic claims—Islamic scholars declaring themselves Japanese agents, for instance—designed to justify the purge of both secular nationalists and religious figures. Uzbek historians further note that internal betrayal compounded the terror: some Uzbek officials and writers denounced their colleagues, eager to settle scores or demonstrate loyalty to the regime.¹⁸ “*Our own people were among the perpetrators... Uzbek investigators took part; some of our writers, scholars, and statesmen turned out to be betrayers*” who facilitated the purges. This toxic atmosphere of denunciation, fear, and violence “burned fiercely” and engulfed the entire society in tragedy.¹⁹

¹⁶ Shamsutdinov, R., *История Узбекистана XX век* (Tashkent: Shark, 2000).

¹⁷ *Podrobno.uz*, “V Uzbekistane v gody sovetsoi vlasti byli repressirovani 100 tisyach chelovek,” 31.08.2020, *Podrobno.uz*, accessed. 11.08.2025.

¹⁸ Shamsutdinov, *ibid*.

¹⁹ Fitzpatrick. *Ibid*.

By the end of 1938, Stalin’s purge in Uzbekistan had eradicated an entire generation of national leaders and cultural figures. Archival records indicate that between 1934 and 1938, over 40,000 individuals in the Uzbek SSR were subjected to repression, with at least 730 officially recorded executions as ‘enemies of the people.’ More recent estimates, drawing on post-Soviet archival research, suggest a far higher toll. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s office revealed that between 1937 and 1953, approximately 100,000 people in Uzbekistan were repressed and 13,000 executed—of whom some 7,000 were put to death in 1937–38 alone. The Great Terror thus devastated not only the party elite and intelligentsia, but also the broader population, as ‘no segment of society’ was spared.²⁰

Cultural Consequences

The cultural impact of the 1937–38 purges on Uzbekistan was catastrophic. The loss of so many leading intellectuals, writers, and scholars created a cultural void that fundamentally altered the trajectory of Uzbek literature, arts, and education. As one analysis notes, the purges “obliterated the generation of older Uzbek intelligentsia and replaced it with more compliant, generally poorly-educated cadres”.²¹ Indeed, the revered generation of Jadid writers and thinkers was largely gone by 1938 – executed, imprisoned, or silenced – and with them went a wealth of linguistic and creative expertise that had been driving Uzbek culture’s modernization.

The executions of Abdulla Qodiriy, Cho’lpon, and Abdurauf Fitrat in 1938 brought an abrupt end to Uzbekistan’s nascent literary renaissance. Their works were immediately banned, and even the possession of manuscripts in Arabic-script Uzbek became perilous. By the late 1930s, merely having ‘a book in Arabic script’ could bring arrest: in 1939 an elderly woman in Khorezm was imprisoned

²⁰ Shavkat Mirziyoyev, Presidential address on the Day of Remembrance of Victims of Repression (31 August 2017, 2019) – official figures released by the Commission for the Rehabilitation of Victims of Political Repressions.

²¹ William Fierman, “Uzbek Feelings of Ethnicity: A Study of Attitudes Expressed in Recent Uzbek Literature,” *Cahiers du Monde Russe* 22, no. 2–3 (1981): p. 192

simply for reading a religious text, and she died in custody. The Soviet state promoted the Cyrillic alphabet (introduced for Uzbek in 1940) as a means of severing links with pre-Soviet written culture. The purged writers’ novels, poems, and plays remained unpublished for decades. An editor who sought to include Cho’lpon’s verses in a 1968 poetry anthology was censured and punished by Soviet authorities. Thereafter, Uzbek literature that appeared in print was almost exclusively authored by ‘new’ Soviet writers, who survived by conforming to Socialist Realism. The result was a literary culture stripped of the critical, experimental, and reformist spirit embodied by the Jadids of the 1920s.²²

Beyond literature, the purges decimated Uzbekistan’s artistic and scholarly institutions. The country’s pioneering filmmakers, theater directors, and artists—many of whom had been experimenting with new forms—were either executed or silenced. The first Uzbek film director, Khudoybergan Devonov, was executed in 1938, halting the republic’s nascent cinematic movement. Newspapers and journals were purged of ‘nationalist’ editors and journalists; the main daily was renamed from Qizil O‘zbekiston to Sovet O‘zbekistoni, and issues from 1937 regularly announced the exposure of correspondents as ‘enemies of the people.’ Censorship tightened dramatically: any work that even subtly challenged Stalinist narratives was prohibited. Some surviving intellectuals sought to evade censorship through allegory and Aesopian language. As one Turkish study notes, a few Uzbek writers attempted to overcome Stalinist constraints by using allegory, symbolism, and veiled criticism. Yet such nuance was perilous, and most artists either self-censored or confined themselves to regime-sanctioned themes. The overall effect was cultural conformism: the vibrant diversity of Uzbek arts and media was replaced by a narrow Soviet orthodoxy.²³

²² Northrop, *ibid.*; Martin, *ibid.*; Uzbek memorial essays on Cho’lpon, Qodiriy, Fitrat (kh-davron.uz).

²³ Abdullaev, *ibid.*; Shamsutdinov, *ibid.*; Sheila Fitzpatrick, *The Cultural Front: Power and Culture in Revolutionary Russia* (Cornell University Press, 1992).

The Great Purge devastated Uzbekistan’s educational and research institutions. In the 1930s, many honest teachers were repressed as ‘enemies of the people,’ with professors and even schoolteachers arrested or executed. Entire departments were emptied: Uzbekistan’s leading Orientalists, historians, and linguists were purged on accusations of fostering nationalist history. The historian Pulat Soliev, pioneer of Uzbek national historiography, was executed in 1938. The removal of so many pedagogues led to what Uzbek historians describe as a ‘catastrophic decrease in the number of educational personnel.’ Schools and universities were left with a vacuum of qualified staff; replacements were politically vetted but often inexperienced. Intellectual inquiry withered under fear: students and teachers dared not discuss topics such as Uzbek history or literature beyond the official Soviet line. Research on Uzbek language, literature, and folklore—once advanced by Fitrat and his colleagues—virtually ceased, stigmatized as ‘bourgeois nationalist scholarship.’ Instead, Soviet ideology dictated a wholesale rewriting of history and culture, forcing scholars to produce Soviet-centric narratives and denounce their own mentors. This purge produced a grievous brain drain and disrupted the transmission of knowledge to future generations. Only during the thaw of the 1950s–60s did Uzbek academia slowly begin to rehabilitate these fields, and even then, the process remained partial and tightly controlled.²⁴

Stalinist repression reshaped language and cultural policy in Central Asia. The Uzbek script was changed twice within little more than a decade—first from Arabic to Latin in 1929, then from Latin to Cyrillic in 1940—a process explicitly intended to sever new generations from pre-revolutionary texts and pan-Turkic connections. Many of the intellectuals who had championed the Latin script and pioneered modern Uzbek terminology were purged, replaced by Moscow-loyal officials who enforced the Soviet linguistic line. The result was accelerated

²⁴ Shamsutdinov, *ibid.*; Fitzpatrick, *ibid.*; Robert Conquest, *ibid.*

Russification: Russian became the prestige language in administration, higher education, and science, while Uzbek was relegated to a simplified idiom for mass consumption. Uzbek-language publishing declined sharply in both quality and quantity after 1938, as so many writers and editors had been eliminated. Educational curricula were reoriented to glorify Stalin and Russian culture, while the works of purged Uzbek authors disappeared from textbooks. The long-term cultural consequence was a rupture in historical continuity: post-purge generations grew up largely unaware of the rich Uzbek modernist literature of the 1910s–20s, which only reemerged during glasnost in the late 1980s.²⁵

In summary, the Stalinist purges of 1937–38 in Uzbekistan dealt a devastating blow to the nation’s cultural life. An entire generation of talent – “*the golden heritage of the nation*” – was erased. This not only caused personal tragedies and silenced voices, but also stunted the development of Uzbek arts and letters for decades. The trauma ensured that those cultural figures who survived (or rose in the aftermath) practiced self-censorship and hewed to socialist realism, lest they meet a similar fate. The vibrant diversity and creative freedom of the 1920s Uzbek intellectual scene were thus replaced by a monochrome culture under tight Party control – a direct consequence of Stalinist repression.

Memory and Representation

The memory of the 1937–1938 purges of Uzbek intellectuals has evolved through suppression, rediscovery, and official commemoration. Under Stalin and his immediate successors, any open discussion of the purges was forbidden. The executed writers and leaders were erased from official history – their books were removed from libraries, their names became taboo in print. Families of victims were stigmatized as “traitors’ kin” and often faced continued persecution (the Soviet slogan “*сын за отца*” – “a son answers for the father” – meant many children of purged intellectuals were barred from education or arrested

²⁵ Khalid, *ibid*; Martin, *ibid*.

themselves). For example, one memoir by Otajon Polvonov recalls that as late as 1950, he – the son of a labeled “enemy of the people” – was himself arrested and nearly executed simply for petitioning for students’ welfare, before being sent to the Gulag. Such experiences bred a deep fear that kept families silent about their martyred relatives for decades.

A few memoirs and oral histories from survivors and relatives did quietly circulate. In Uzbekistan, some family members held on to letters or memories; these formed an “*underground memory*” of the lost intelligentsia. For instance, the wife of an executed writer, Saodat Qodiriy, lived to tell her story – described in sources as “Three Lives of Saodat: Communist, Uzbek, survivor” – reflecting the personal cost of the purges.²⁶ In general, though, until the late 1980s there were only whisper networks and hidden manuscripts (many works of Cho’lpon and Fitrat survived only in secret copies cherished by friends). As one account notes, “*Cho’lpon’s works were passed around secretly*” in samizdat, and he “*remained persona non grata until the fall of the Soviet Union*”.²⁷

The Khrushchev Thaw of the mid-1950s initiated the first wave of rehabilitations. Following Khrushchev’s 1956 denunciation of Stalin’s crimes at the 20th Party Congress, Soviet authorities began gradually clearing the names of purged victims. In Uzbekistan, rehabilitation proceeded slowly: while many lesser-known figures were exonerated during the late 1950s, key political leaders such as Fayzulla Khodjaev and Akmal Ikramov were only officially rehabilitated in 1965. By contrast, leading cultural figures—including Qodiriy, Cho’lpon, and Fitrat—remained officially banned until the glasnost era of the late 1980s.²⁸ However, rehabilitation often remained abstract – names were cleared in archives but not necessarily publicized. A courageous attempt in 1968 to publicly honor

²⁶ Marianne Kamp, “Three Lives of Saodat: Communist, Uzbek, Survivor,” *The Oral History Review* 28, no. 2 (2001): 21+, Gale Academic OneFile, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A80500449/AONE?u=anon-48789b19&sid=googleScholar&xid=19ba57e7>, accessed 20.08.2025.

²⁷ Tim Brinkhof, “3 Subversive Books That Managed to Sneak Past Soviet Censorship,” *Big Think — High Culture*, 22.05.2023.

²⁸ Shamsutdinov, *ibid*; Getty & Naumov, *ibid*.

Cho’lpon in print was quashed by censors, indicating that the full story of 1937 was still too sensitive. It was only during glasnost (late 1980s) that Uzbek media and scholars began openly revisiting the Great Terror. Articles and books emerged detailing the fates of the “repressesees” (*qurbonlar* or *qatag’on qurbonlari* in Uzbek). Families could finally speak, and the public learned the true scope of the tragedy that “*hundreds of Uzbek intellectuals were shot in 1937-38 for their nation’s freedom*”. Uzbek historians and writers of the late Soviet period published lists of victims and started calling 1937 “Katta qirg’in” (“the Great Massacre”).²⁹ This reclaiming of memory was integral to the national consciousness in the perestroika years leading up to independence.

After Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, the formerly repressed intellectuals were elevated as national heroes and martyrs. The new government under Islam Karimov sought to build an Uzbek national narrative that honored these victims of Stalinism as symbols of both the suffering and resilience of the nation. Streets and schools were named after Qodiriy, Cho’lpon, Fitrat and others. Their works were republished and integrated into curricula (often in restored original Uzbek editions). In 2000, Abdulla Qodiriy’s famous novel *O’tgan Kunlar* (*Days Gone By*) was finally printed in its uncensored form and made required reading, a stark reversal from the Soviet ban. Monographs and documentaries about the purged figures appeared, and scholars critically revisited Stalinist policies. Uzbek archivists gained limited access to NKVD files, enabling more accurate counts and biographies of victims to be compiled.

In independent Uzbekistan, a Day of Remembrance for Victims of Repression was formally instituted on 31 August—the eve of Independence Day—establishing a symbolic link between the struggle for national sovereignty and the memory of those martyred under Soviet rule.³⁰ In 2002, the “Shahidlar Xotirasi” (Martyrs’ Memory) memorial and museum was inaugurated in

²⁹ UZREPORT TV. “1934–1938-yillarda O‘zbekistondan 40 ming nafardan ortiq insonlar qatag’on qilingan.” YouTube video, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f-gw0vlz7aA>, accessed: 20.08.2025.

³⁰ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi qarori, 200; Khalid, *ibid.*, p. 365.

Tashkent’s Yunusabad district, at the very site where the 1938 executions of leading Uzbek intellectuals and officials had taken place.³¹ The museum documents the fate of repression victims, displaying photographs, manuscripts, and personal effects of figures such as Abdulla Qodiriy and Abdurauf Fitrat.³² Each year on 31 August, the country’s leadership lays flowers at the memorial and prayers (*du’ā*) are recited. In his commemorative speeches, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has openly acknowledged the scale of the tragedy: “Between 1937 and 1953, about 100,000 people in Uzbekistan were repressed and 13,000 mercilessly shot... In 1937–38 alone about 7,000 were executed.”³³ He described them as “the true leaders, the foremost intellectuals, the flower of our nation.”³⁴ Such initiatives, along with academic studies and journalistic accounts, mark an earnest effort to reclaim historical memory and integrate the narrative of repression into Uzbekistan’s national identity.

However, the path to full remembrance has not been without challenges. Under Islam Karimov’s rule (1991–2016), while the narrative of Stalinist repression was officially promoted, some critics argue that it was also selectively instrumentalized to bolster regime legitimacy.³⁵ For example, 4 October 2015—the anniversary of the 1938 mass execution—passed without official commemoration, leading observers to note a certain ambivalence or “amnesia.” Radio Ozodlik reported that Uzbekistan “did not commemorate the day of the execution of the Uzbek intelligentsia” in 2015, despite appeals by historians.³⁶ This suggests that public remembrance has fluctuated, shaped in part by political

³¹ “Shahidlar Xotirasi Majmuasi,” Shahidlar Xotirasi Memorial Complex <http://www.shahidlarxotirasi.uz>, accessed: 19.08.2025.

³² Shamsutdinov, *ibid.*

³³ Shavkat Mirziyoyev, “If Not for Repression, They Could Have Done Great Deeds,” *UzDaily*, August 31, 2017, <https://www.uzdaily.uz/en/shavkat-mirziyoyev-if-not-for-repression-they-could-have-done-great-deeds>, accessed: 19.08.2025.

³⁴ Abdullaev, *ibid.*; also see. “Uzbekistan Establishes Annual Week of Remembrance for Political Repression Victims,” *Kun.uz*, 20.07.2024, <https://kun.uz/en/news/2024/07/20/uzbekistan-establishes-annual-week-of-remembrance-for-political-repression-victims>, accessed: 19.08.2025.

³⁵ Khalid, *ibid.*, ss. 370–372; Marianne Kamp, “Recollections of Repression: Women’s Voices in Uzbekistan,” *Central Asian Survey* 26, no. 2 (2007): pp. 205–222.

³⁶ O‘zbekiston 4-oktyabrni—o‘zbek ziyolilari qatl etilgan kunni eslamadi,” *Radio Ozodlik*, October 4, 2015, <https://www.ozodlik.org/a/27285995.html>, accessed: 19.08.2025.

considerations. Nonetheless, the broader trajectory in post-Soviet Uzbekistan has been toward honoring and researching the repressed intelligentsia. Under President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, initiatives have gone further: in 2020 he ordered comprehensive research into each of the 100,000 repression victims, including contacting descendants, publishing biographical collections, and naming schools and neighborhoods after them.³⁷ This ambitious project seeks to restore individual histories and preserve the martyrs’ legacy for future generations.

Archival Rediscoveries have greatly enriched the understanding of the purges. In the 2010s, Uzbek historians gained access to some KGB archives, uncovering execution lists and interrogation records. These findings have clarified, for example, the exact execution date and burial site of the literary figures (confirming that Qodiriy, Cho’lpon, and Fitrat were executed on 4 October 1938 in Tashkent, not exiled to Siberia as some rumors once held). Archeological surveys at the execution ground (Qorasuv/Aqtape) in the 2010s uncovered remains and personal items, which have been reinterred with proper Islamic rites. Such tangible evidence lends weight to oral histories. One striking oral account from a researcher describes how in 1953 a mass grave was accidentally unearthed near Tashkent: the bulldozer exposed “*bones piled like firewood*” along with remnants of elegant Uzbek robes, boots, and doppis (caps), clearly belonging to elite individuals. Locals immediately suspected these were the 1938 victims, recognizing that “*these were Jadids – their attire was very fine*”, and later historical proof corroborated their identities. Stories like this have become part of the collective memory and underscore the importance of memorializing these sites.

In Uzbek literature and arts, the legacy of the purged generation has been reasserted. Memoirs and novels now openly depict the purge years – for example,

³⁷ “Shavkat Mirziyoyev: Har bir qatag’on qurboni haqida to’liq ma’lumotlar yig’iladi,” *Kun.uz*, August 31, 2020, <https://kun.uz/uz/news/2020/08/31/shavkat-mirziyoyev-har-bir-qatag-on-qurboni-haqida-toliq-malumotlar-yigiladi>; see also “In 1937–1953, 100 Thousand People Were Repressed in Uzbekistan, 13 Thousand Were Mercilessly Shot,” *UzDaily*, August 31, 2017.

some writers have penned historical fiction about the lives and trials of Qodiriy and Cho’lpon, and stage plays have been produced dramatizing their last hours. Biographical research in Uzbek and Russian (including works by T. Qahhor on Cho’lpon, and various monographs on Fitrat) compile letters from the NKVD archives and personal recollections, building a fuller picture of these individuals’ contributions and suffering. Meanwhile, Western scholarship has also engaged with this topic: English-language historians like Adeeb Khalid have contextualized the fate of Uzbek intellectuals within Soviet nationalities policy, and recent studies compare experiences across Soviet minority intelligentsias. These scholarly works (often available in Russian or Uzbek translation) are cited in Uzbek academic conferences and help frame the collective trauma of 1937–38 as both a national tragedy and part of the broader Stalinist terror.

Today, the representation of the 1937–38 purges in Uzbekistan’s public discourse is one of solemn reverence. The victims are portrayed as martyrs who “fought for the freedom of their nation” and whose martyrdom became a cornerstone of Uzbekistan’s 20th-century history. School textbooks include chapters on the “*Stalin qatag’oni*” (Stalinist repressions), often listing Qodiriy, Fitrat, Cho’lpon, Ikramov, Khodjaev and others as national heroes who were unjustly killed. At the same time, this memory serves as a cautionary tale about totalitarianism: it emphasizes the value of independence and cultural revival after the collapse of the Soviet Union. Uzbek filmmakers have produced documentaries and even feature films portraying the purge era, which contribute to public memory. In sum, after long decades of enforced silence, Uzbekistan has, since independence, endeavored to memorialize and learn from the horrors of 1937–1938. The rehabilitated intellectuals now occupy their rightful place in the pantheon of Uzbek culture, ensuring that the cultural consequences of Stalinist repression – the void it created and the heritage it nearly destroyed – are neither forgotten nor in vain.

CONCLUSION

The 1937–1938 purges in Uzbekistan stand as a pivotal moment in the history of Soviet Central Asia. By eliminating nearly the entire generation of national intellectuals, Stalin’s regime inflicted irreparable damage on the cultural foundations of Uzbek society. The executions of leading writers, scholars, and educators halted a burgeoning literary and intellectual renaissance and replaced it with decades of ideological conformity. The void left by figures such as Qodiriy, Cho‘lpon, and Fitrat deprived Uzbekistan of its most creative voices and reshaped cultural production under the strict dictates of socialist realism.

Beyond the immediate loss of lives, the purges severed historical continuity: language reforms, censorship, and the destruction of archives combined to obscure pre-Soviet cultural memory. The intellectual trauma extended into education, literature, and the arts, where fear and self-censorship became enduring features. Yet, the long-suppressed memory of these repressions has resurfaced in post-Soviet Uzbekistan, where commemoration and rehabilitation efforts seek to honor the victims as martyrs of national culture. Museums, memorials, and public narratives now inscribe their legacies into the story of Uzbek independence and identity.

Ultimately, the Stalinist repression of Uzbek intellectuals was not merely a political purge but a cultural catastrophe that reshaped the trajectory of an entire nation. Understanding its historical and cultural consequences is essential not only for grasping the dynamics of Soviet rule but also for recognizing the resilience of Uzbek identity in the face of systematic attempts at erasure.

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